

Implementation of waste management policy in Morowali Regency (Study of waste management in Bahodopi District)

Hayundwitama¹, Nasir Mangngasing², Nuraisyah³, Djibril H. Kawuree⁴

Tadulako University, Indonesia¹⁻³, Professor Iya Abubakar Community Resources Centre Bauchi, Nigeria⁴

*Corresponding author: hayundwitama@gmail.com

Abstract

This research is to determine the implementation of waste management policies in Morowali Regency. Waste Management Study in Bahodopi District. The type of research used is descriptive qualitative. Data types use primary data and secondary data. Data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews and documentation. The informant withdrawal technique purpose uses. The data analysis used is the Miles, Huberman and Saldana model, namely data collection, data presentation, data condensation and drawing conclusions. The waste problem in Bahodopi District is basically the responsibility of all parties, including the community, companies and local government. The habit of people who like to throw rubbish out of place makes waste management in this area increasingly ineffective and difficult to overcome. This habit of throwing rubbish carelessly is caused by a lack of education and facilities at rubbish dumps and final disposal sites. In fact, the current increase in population in Bahodopi District will have an impact on the balance of the city, including waste production. The greater the population of an area, the more waste produced every day will also increase. Based on the results of research conducted, the Implementation of Waste Management Policy in Morowali Regency. The Waste Management Study in Bahodopi District is relatively ineffective, there are still many problems that need to be resolved so that waste handling can be more optimal, starting from the aspects of communication, socialization, resources and bureaucratic structure, all of which have different problems from one another, so government and community commitment to carry out waste management consistently.

Keywords: [policy](#), [management](#), [waste](#), [government and society](#)

Introduction

The law states that a healthy environment is the right of every citizen. Article 65 paragraph 1 of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection and Management reads: "every person has the right to a good and healthy living environment as part of human rights". In the article above it is clear that everyone deserves a good and healthy living environment for a better future and more secure health. A good and healthy environment can be realized one way by realizing good waste management and synergistic movements to overcome it. Likewise with the implementation of waste management in Bahodopi District. Waste has become a problem for the local government, so its management needs to be carried out in a comprehensive and integrated manner from upstream to downstream so that it provides economic benefits, is healthy for the community and safe for the environment and can change community behavior.

Morowali Regency Regional Regulation, Number 5 of 2017 concerning Waste Management, states that the government, private sector and society should pay more attention to aspects of environmental management and protection. Including in waste management, every

person has the right to receive services in waste management in a good and environmentally sound manner from the Government, Regional Government, and/or other parties who are given responsibility and participate in the decision-making, implementation and supervision process in the field of waste management. In article 1 paragraph 2, which is stated in the Law on Environmental Protection and Management, it is explained that protecting and managing the environment is an integrated and systematic effort carried out with the aim of making the environment always sustainable and efforts to prevent pollution and environmental damage, namely with planning, utilization, control, maintenance, supervision and law enforcement.

Increasing environmental pollution is caused by various things, such as the increase in human population which results in an increase in the amount of waste thrown away. This is exacerbated by the lack of adequate places and locations for waste disposal, the lack of awareness and willingness of the community to manage and dispose of waste, the lack of public understanding about the benefits of waste, and the reluctance of the community to reuse waste, because waste is considered something dirty and must be thrown away or it is prestigious. These various things cause a decline in environmental quality which has a negative impact on society.

Environmental problems have actually been going on for a long time, even without human intervention. Environmental damage and pollution are increasingly accelerating due to increasing human activity and greedy human nature. Environmental problems not only occur in developing countries, but also in developed (industrial) countries. Environmental problems can be caused by various activities, both on a limited (narrow) scale and on a wide scale. Rapid (high) population growth in a region or country will certainly cause various environmental problems.

This waste problem is increasing from year to year. With the increasing number of community activities that are not balanced by landfills and efforts to process waste into something useful again. This is caused by the accumulation of waste which both affects environmental damage and changes in public health conditions so that there is no comfort for urban communities. Trash is an expression that is generally used to express waste, items that are no longer used. Waste has three forms, namely solid, liquid and gas waste. However, in general trash is only used to represent solid waste. Furthermore, this waste problem has caused a lot of anxiety. The things that most often arise are environmental problems such as water pollution, air pollution, the emergence of unpleasant odors and decreased air quality, the greenhouse effect, and becoming a breeding ground for diseases such as mosquitoes. The most important thing is that waste has an impact on society in the form of security, comfort, public health and welfare. Waste has now become a problem and challenge in urban and rural areas.

The definition of waste written in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 18 of 2008 concerning Waste Management is that waste is the remainder of human activities and daily activities and is a natural process in solid form. Waste processing in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 18 of 2008 concerning Waste Management, namely an activity to reduce and handle waste in a systematic, sustainable manner. The waste processing system in Indonesia is generally still considered traditional and often ends up turning into waste disposal practices. The increase in the amount of waste is often not offset by a good waste processing system. This increasing amount of waste will not be able to be managed well if it is still handled using the old paradigm (collection, transport and throw away).

In fact, waste is still an environmental problem in various areas, including in Bahodopi District, Morowali Regency. This waste problem requires the role of all levels of society from local residents, communities, government institutions and even industry players. This waste problem occurs in several areas, especially large cities with large populations, which currently leaves various kinds of problems. Responsibility for waste management in Bahodopi District is

held by the Morowali Regency Environmental Service. Waste management in Bahodopi District still uses the old paradigm, namely collection-disposal. Based on data obtained by researchers, currently in Bahodopi District alone, waste production has reached 80 tons per day per day. Based on the estimated calculations, each individual will produce at least 1/2-kilogram of waste per day from unused necessities. Even piles of household rubbish were seen at several points in Bahodopi District, Morowali Regency. Almost all villages in Bahodopi District are littered with piles of rubbish on the side of the Trans Sulawesi Road. Some have even gone down the irrigation canals and blocked the water flow. Piles of rubbish can be seen from Lalampu Village, Bahodopi to Labota Village and the worst is in Labota Village. Labota Village Head Ahmar admitted that the uncontrolled waste in his village was due to several factors. These include a lack of public awareness, the condition of the number of waste trucks being only 1 unit and the location of the Final Waste Disposal Site (TPA) being far away. The waste produced by my community reaches up to 80 (forty) tons a day. <https://www.metrosulteng.com/government/pr-5193676281/pemda-morowali-diminta-turun-tangan-atasi-problem-sampah-di-bahadopi>

Waste that is not transported will cause problems, namely health and the environment, so that it can cause various diseases, dirty housing, unpleasant odors, reduce the capacity of rivers and so on and ultimately this has an impact on increasingly scarce places for waste disposal and production. more and more rubbish. This caused the spread of TPS in various places on empty land and in rivers in the Bahodopi District area.

Referring to the description above, referring to the initial observations made by prospective researchers, there are still many problems that have not yet been resolved by the Morowali Regency Environmental Service and the Bahodopi District apparatus, including the village government in the Bahodopi District area. As for these various problems, when linked to Edward III's theoretical approach in Indiahono (2009:31-34), it can be said that there is still a lack of communication between Bahodopi District officials and the Village Government, which has resulted in minimal outreach to the community. The communication that exists between the Environmental Service and the community, business actors and the media is not very effective and interactive, so it is still one-way. There is no reciprocity from the community and business actors. The community and business actors only carry out their duties, namely managing their waste independently. Another problem is that resources are still very limited which greatly influences this policy, namely the number of waste operational vehicles is very limited while the volume of waste is increasing every day.

Apart from that, the criminal sanctions and fines contained in the Morowali Regency Regional Regulation, Number 5 of 2017 concerning Waste Management, have not yet been consistently realized. In fact, the regulation explains that people who manage waste that causes environmental pollution and/or damage, throw rubbish into environmental media or not in designated and/or provided places and burn rubbish in open spaces which is not in accordance with the technical requirements for waste management. will be threatened with imprisonment for a maximum of 3 (three) months or a fine of a maximum of IDR 50,000,000.00 (Fifty Million Rupiah). However, in reality these sanctions and fines have never been implemented, resulting in no deterrent effect on society.

Public Policy Concept

The word policy, according to William N. Dunn, quoted by Abidin in his book entitled public policy (2012:4), suggests that etymologically policy comes from the Greek word polis which means city-state. In Latin, this word changed to politia which means country. Entering old

English (the Middle English), the word became *policie*, the meaning of which is related to government affairs or government administration.

Meanwhile, public policy, according to Chandler and Plano in Keban (2004: 56), states that: "public policy is the strategic use of existing resources to solve public or government problems". Even Chandler and Plano also think that public policy is a form of continuous intervention by the government in the interests of powerless people in society so that they can live and participate in government. Here it can be seen that policy is not merely seen as a strategic utilization of resources, but also has a very deep, even decisive, moral dimension.

Furthermore, Lasswell, in his book *power personality*, quoted by Parsons (2011: 19), said that a science is called policy science if it explains the process of policy making in society, or provides the data needed to make rational decisions regarding certain issues. Under these circumstances we need to develop strategies to defend and expand our values using our limited intellectual resources. The term "policy" is used to indicate the need for explanation of social goals that must be provided by the scientific field.

Policy is a fundamental decision to be used as a basis for action in an effort to achieve predetermined goals. Policy is also one of the government's tools in carrying out its duties and functions which binds all components of the nation within it. Therefore, policy is state administration, because state administration involves formulating and implementing public needs. Meanwhile, public policy, when viewed from an instrumental perspective, is a tool to achieve a goal related to the government's efforts to realize public values. Public values as policy objectives can take various forms. Thus, in general, public policy can be interpreted as a tool to realize the ideal values of society such as justice, equality and openness, as well as trying to solve the problems faced by society.

Public policy, according to Dunn (2003: 132), states that: "a complex dependency pattern of interdependent collective choices, including decisions not to act, made by government agencies or offices". Easton in Islamy (2009:19), gives the meaning of state policy as: "the authoritative allocation of values for the whole society". (forced (legal) allocation of values to all members of society).

The definition above emphasizes that only the government can legally do something to society and the government's choice to do something or not do something is in the form of allocating values to society. This is because the government is included in what Easton calls "authorities in a political system", namely the rulers in a political system who are involved in everyday problems which have become their responsibility or role.

Concept of Public Policy Implementation

Mazmanian and Sabatier's formulation in Widodo (2010:87), explains that the meaning of implementation is: "To understand what actually happens after a program is enacted or formulated is the subject of policy implementation. Those events and activities that occur after the issuance of authoritative public policy directives, which include both the effort to administer and the substantive impacts on people and events". (This means that the main essence of policy implementation is understanding what should happen after a program is declared effective or formulated. This understanding includes efforts to administer it and to cause a real impact on society or events).

Based on the meaning above, this definition not only involves the behavior of administrative bodies responsible for implementing programs and engendering obedience in target groups, but also involves a network of political, economic and social forces that can

directly or indirectly influence the behavior of all parties involved and ultimately have an impact on what is expected (intended) and unintended (unintended) of a program”.

In principle, policy implementation refers to the activities of carrying out policies in the actual domain, whether carried out by government organs or the parties specified in the policy. The implementation of the policy itself is usually called the implementing party and the target group. Policy implementers are those who are officially recognized as individuals/institutions responsible for implementing programs in the field. The target group is to designate the parties who are used as policy objects. However, in practice, policy implementation is a very complex process, often even politically charged with the intervention of various interests.

According to Edward III, policy implementation is the decision-making stage between the formation of a policy, such as the articles of a Legislative law, the issuance of an Executive regulation, the passing of a court decision, or the issuance of regulatory standards, and the consequences of the policy for society which affects several aspects of its life . So, if a policy is taken correctly, the possibility of failure can still occur, if the implementation process is not appropriate, but even a brilliant policy, if implemented poorly, can fail to achieve the goals of its designers (Tangkilisan, 2003: 1-2)

Policy Implementation Models

Mazmanian and Sabatier in Subarsono (2005:94-98), say that there are 3 (three) groups of variables that influence the success of implementation, namely: Characteristics of the problem, Characteristics of the policy/Law and Policy environment variables.

- 1) Problem Characteristics (tractability of the problems).
- 2) Policy Characteristics (ability of statute to structure implementation).
- 3) Policy environment (nonstatutory variables affecting implementation).

These aspects of implementation are explained by Van Meter and Van Horn in Nawawi (2009:139-141), as follows:

- 1) Policy standards and targets. Every public policy must have standards and a clear and measurable policy target. With these provisions the goal can be realized. Policy standards and targets are not clear, so multiple interpretations cannot occur and easily give rise to misunderstandings and conflicts between implementing agents.
- 2) Implementation resources. In implementing a policy, resource support is needed, both human resources, material resources and method resources. Of these three resources, the most important is human resources, because apart from being the subject of policy implementation, it is also an object of public policy.
- 3) Inter-organizational communication. In many policy implementation programs, as a reality, policy programs require good relations between related agencies, namely communication and coordination support. For this reason, coordination and cooperation between agencies is needed for the success of a program. Communication and coordination are the lifeblood of an organization so that the program can be realized with its goals and objectives.
- 4) Characteristics of the implementing agency. In order to achieve maximum success in implementing a policy, the characteristics of the implementing agent must be identified and known, including the bureaucratic structure, norms and relationship patterns that occur within the bureaucracy, all of which will influence the implementation of a predetermined policy program.
- 5) Implementor disposition. In policy implementation, the implementor's attitude or disposition is divided into three things, namely: a) The implementor's response to the policy, which is related to the implementor's willingness to implement public policy; b) Conditions, namely

understanding of the policies that have been established; c) The intensity of the implementor's disposition, namely the value preferences they have.

- 6) Environmental, social, economic and political conditions. This variable includes environmental economic resources that can support successful policy implementation, the extent to which interest groups provide support for policy implementation; characteristics of the participants, namely support or rejection; what is the nature of public opinion in the environment and whether the political elite supports policy implementation.

The formulation of policy implementation according to Edward III, quoted by Indiahono (2009:31-34), states that the variables that play a major role in achieving an implementation consist of 4 (four) variables, namely: communication, resources, disposition (attitude of the implementer), and structure bureaucracy.

- 1) Communication, namely indicating that each policy will be implemented well if there is effective communication between program (policy) implementers and the target group (target group). The goals and objectives of programs/policies can be socialized properly so as to avoid distortion of policies and programs. This is important because the higher the target group's knowledge of the program, the lower the level of rejection and mistakes in applying programs and policies in the real world.
- 2) Resources, namely indicating that every policy must be supported by adequate resources, both human resources and financial resources. Human resources are sufficient quality and quantity of implementers to cover the entire target group. Financial resources are sufficient investment capital for a program/policy. Both must be considered in implementing government programs/policies. Because without the reliability of the implementer, policies will be less energetic and run slowly and haphazardly. Meanwhile, financial resources guarantee the sustainability of programs/policies. Without adequate financial support, the program cannot run effectively and quickly in achieving goals and targets.
- 3) Disposition, namely designating characteristics that are closely attached to policy/program implementers. The important characteristics an implementor has are honesty, commitment and democracy. Implementors who have high commitment and are honest will always survive the obstacles encountered in the program/policy. Honesty directs implementers to remain within the program levels outlined in the program guidelines. His commitment and honesty made him even more enthusiastic in implementing the program stages consistently. A democratic attitude will increase the good impression of the implementer and the policy before members of the target group.
- 4) Bureaucratic Structure, which indicates that bureaucratic structure is important in implementing policies. This aspect of bureaucratic structure includes two important things, first is the mechanism and structure of the implementing organization. The program implementation mechanism is usually determined through standard operating procedures (SOP) which are included in the program/policy guidelines. A good standard operating procedure (SOP) includes a framework that is clear, systematic, not complicated and easy to understand by anyone, because it will be a reference for the implementor's work. Meanwhile, the implementing organizational structure, as far as possible, avoids things that are convoluted, long and complex.

The four variables mentioned above have a very important relationship, one variable with other variables in achieving program/policy goals and objectives. Everything is in synergy with each other in achieving the goal and one variable will greatly influence the other variables. This implementation model from Edward III can be used as a tool to image program implementation

in various places and times. This means that the 4 (four) variables available in the model can be used to describe the phenomenon of public policy implementation.

The type of research used is descriptive qualitative. Sugiyono (2007) stated that "Descriptive research is research carried out to determine the value of independent variables, either one or more variables (independent) without making comparisons, or connecting one variable with another variable" therefore the appropriate approach in this research through qualitative research methods. Qualitative is to describe a situation or phenomenon based on visible or real facts, so in analyzing the data that has been collected, it is not tested statistically, but rather non-statistical analysis in accordance with descriptive research.

Qualitative research begins with collecting information in appropriate situations, to formulate it into a generalization that can be accepted by human common sense. The problem to be revealed can be prepared before collecting data (information) but may develop and change during research activities. In this way, the data (information) collected is focused on spoken sentences, written sentences and visible behavior or activities. The information is studied and interpreted with an effort to understand its meaning according to the point of view of the data source. The meaning of special information in theoretical form through a qualitative research process is not impossible to produce new theories, not just for practical purposes.

Data types use primary data and secondary data. Data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews and documentation. The informant withdrawal technique uses purpose. The data analysis used is the Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014) model, namely data collection, data presentation, data condensation and drawing conclusions.

Implementation of Waste Management Policy in Morowali Regency (Study of Waste Management in Bahodopi District)

Cleanliness is a general phenomenon that needs to be managed well and professionally in order to create a clean, beautiful, healthy, friendly and orderly environment. To ensure the realization of environmental cleanliness as a whole and continuously, every member of society must be aware and appreciate that cleanliness is part of religious teachings and it is necessary to cultivate a culture of environmental cleanliness, both individually and cooperatively. Environmental issues have also been emphasized in the 1945 Constitution in article 28 paragraph (1) where it is emphasized that every citizen has the right to obtain a good and healthy living environment from the state. To follow up on this article, the government is obliged to provide public services in the environmental sector in order to create good and healthy conditions for society as mandated in the constitution.

The issue of cleanliness is closely related to the problem of waste. Waste is an important issue in urban environmental problems faced in line with population growth and increased development activities. The increase in waste volume is growing exponentially which has not been accompanied by a commensurate increase in Regional Government revenues for municipal waste management. Waste is one of the environmental problems that cannot be handled properly, especially in big cities. The ability to manage and handle waste is not balanced with production, so waste piles up everywhere. Waste that is not managed properly will cause a decline in the health and aesthetic value of the environment due to water and air pollution and the development of pests and diseases. Waste management planning is a complex problem, it is not enough just to be carried out by government officials, but must involve the private sector and every household, with waste handling depending on the cooperation and awareness of every household,

community, private sector and government in storing, collecting, carrying and hoarding. waste with good coordination and arrangement of waste disposal sites.

The waste problem in Bahodopi District is regulated in several policies contained in the Morowali Regency Regional Regulation, Number 5 of 2017 concerning Waste Management. The aim and objective of the Regional Regulation is to manage cleanliness based on the principles of benefit, fairness and equality, togetherness and kinship as well as environmental sustainability. Cleanliness management aims to create integrated responsibilities between the Regional Government and the community towards a clean, healthy, beautiful and orderly environment. In article 1 paragraph 2, which is stated in the Law on Environmental Protection and Management, it is explained that protecting and managing the environment is an integrated and systematic effort carried out with the aim of making the environment always sustainable and efforts to prevent pollution and environmental damage, namely with planning, utilization, control, maintenance, supervision and law enforcement.

The following are the results of research conducted by researchers regarding the implementation of waste management policies in Morowali Regency, studies on waste management in Bahodopi District, using Edward III's theoretical approach which consists of 4 aspects, namely communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure, explanation of research results namely as follows:

Communication

Abdul Wahab (2005) in his book said that in principle policy communication is communication that occurs within the government, so that it can be translated as conveying government messages, programs and ideas to the public in order to achieve state goals. Policy communication itself has several dimensions, including the dimensions of transformation (transmission), clarity (clarity) and consistency (consistency).

Communication between the Environmental Service and the Bahodopi District is relatively inadequate. One piece of evidence that can support the statements of the two informants is that up to now there is still a lot of rubbish in the Bahodopi District area, in fact there is so much of it, some of the rubbish is dumped in the river area, some of it is even thrown behind residential areas. Thus, the communication that the district had hoped for apparently did not produce results because to date, this communication has not been followed up again. According to researchers, due to inconsistencies on both sides, the victims in this case are the community, because rubbish thrown anywhere will trigger the emergence of various diseases. Thus, communication is the exchange of messages with a number of people within an organization or outside the organization, face to face or through the media.

Basically, communication and socialization are the process of conveying information to every community so that they are willing to comply and comply with all the rules set by the government, of course these rules will not cause difficulties for the community. Policy communication is the process of conveying policy information from policy makers to policy implementers and then socializing it to target groups. Regarding the informant's answer above, researchers can draw the conclusion that there are no prohibitions and strong warnings given by the government so that many people still commit violations. In fact, a strong warning given to the community can minimize the number of people who commit violations.

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it is known that outreach in the form of billboards has often been carried out to the entire community regarding the prohibition on throwing away rubbish. Thus, it can be understood that communication and socialization greatly determine the success of achieving the goals of a policy. However, if the socialization or

delivery of information is not carried out, this will result in the policy being hampered and not running as it should. Therefore, effective implementation will occur if decision makers already know what they are going to implement. Based on information obtained by researchers from an informant who has worked at DLH for a long time, when this policy was first implemented, many people did not know about the existence of this policy, due to a lack of socialization. Therefore, stakeholder involvement is highly demanded in the delivery of this policy, because they are the main key in the successful implementation of this policy. If you look at the reality, socialization is only carried out at the beginning of this regional regulation being implemented.

Resource

According to Van Meter and Van Horn in Subarsono (2011: 100), policy implementation requires support from human resources and support from non-human resources. Apart from human resources, other resources should also be taken into account in implementing waste management policies, such as financial resources and time resources, because while competent and capable human resources are available, they are not supported by financial resources and facilities and infrastructure. In implementing the policy, it will be a complicated problem to realize what the waste management policy aims are. Edward III in Widodo (2010:98) stated that this resource factor also has an important role in policy implementation. Edward III further emphasized that, no matter how clear and consistent the provisions or rules are, and no matter how accurately the delivery of these provisions or rules is, if the policy implementers who are responsible for implementing the policy lack the resources to carry out work effectively, then the implementation of the policy will not be effective. The resources referred to in this research include human resources, financial resources, and equipment/facilities and infrastructure resources needed to implement waste management policies.

Human Resources

Based on the results of research conducted, it is known that up to now, the number of rubbish bins prepared by the government is still very limited, while the population of Bahodopi sub-district is increasing day by day, so that the need for rubbish fleets for the community will automatically increase as well. Thus, there is a kind of dilemma that arises regarding people's attitudes when they want to throw away rubbish. because I'm afraid that throwing it next to the trash can only cause the trash to rot because the trash can is already full. Apart from the facility resources needed to provide protection to people who have the status of passive smokers, the community also needs sufficient information, not only related to how to implement policies, but also knowing the importance (essence) of data regarding the compliance of other parties involved with the rules and regulations apply. The human resources of policy actors (implementers) must influence other people involved in implementing the policy. In addition, human resources who implement policies must also have the necessary authority to implement policies.

Budget Resources

Piles of rubbish along the Trans Sulawesi Road in the Bahodopi District area should be of concern to the Regional Government. The reason is, this pile of rubbish not only disturbs road users because day by day it piles up on the road shoulder until it is strewn across the road, but it also causes an unpleasant odor and can cause flooding because some of the rubbish has covered the water drains or gutters. This condition is very worrying for residents because the piles of rubbish in several villages in Bahodopi District are very worrying. In this case, researchers are of the opinion that, in order to change the behavior (disposition) of policy actors in carrying out

their duties and functions, it is necessary to establish or include an incentive system in the accountability system. The accountability system must include or provide an incentive system for service personnel, and perhaps the community could also be involved, for example hospital visitors who have been looking after their sick families for a long time to be given socialization that is easy for them to understand and understand.

Equipment Resources

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it is known that the equipment used to implement waste management policies requires a combination of the necessary sources, in the sense that on the one hand it must be guaranteed that there are no obstacles to all the required sources, and on the other hand at each stage of the process implementation of a combination between these sources must be truly available. According to researchers, waste handling in the Bahodopi area has not been as expected. So far, all that has been done is collect or clean up locations where there is a buildup of rubbish. Not yet included in the integrated waste management stage. Therefore, many people hope that there will be synchronization of programs from technical OPDs. For example, providing rubbish bins and mobile units to support BumDes in handling waste in their area. Apart from that, we need a representative landfill that can accommodate the household waste of the Bahodopi community. Based on information that researchers received from DLH officials, currently the Regional Government, through the Morowali DLH, has plans to build a landfill in the future located in Bahodopi Village with a land area of around 20 hectares. So, the main responsibility for implementing policies lies with the policy implementer, and generally must be equipped with a number of certain administrative technical skills. So that obstacles that will occur can be anticipated in advance, and fast and appropriate action can be taken immediately. Therefore, without adequate resource support, it is impossible to achieve policy implementation in accordance with the organization's wishes.

Disposition

Edward III in Widodo (2010:104) states that a high disposition influences the level of success of policy implementation. Disposition is defined as the tendency, desire or agreement of implementers to implement a policy. Therefore, the success of a policy implementation is not only determined by the extent to which the policy actors know what must be done and are able to do it, but is also determined by the willingness of the policy actors to have a strong disposition towards the policy being implemented. This disposition is the will, desire and tendency of policy actors to implement policies democratically, honestly, fairly and transparently so that the policy objectives can be realized in accordance with the interests of the target group, especially the implementation of existing waste management policies in Bahodopi District.

There are still people who throw rubbish not in the actual rubbish dump, this is because not all people care about it and want to comply with these rules. In fact, Bahodopi District, as a place where large industries are located, should not be polluted by community waste. However, in reality, the behavior of many community members does not show compliance with these regulations. This shows that there has been no firm action from government officials to take firm action against citizens who heed these rules. Thus, the policy for implementing waste management must also be supported by community compliance and concern regarding the policy, so that the government policy regarding waste management will be able to save the fate of the residents of Bahodopi District as a whole.

Based on what was stated by the informants in this research, according to Edward III, this disposition will emerge among policy actors, when it will benefit not only their organization, but

also themselves. They will know that the policy will benefit the organization and themselves, if they have enough knowledge (cognitive) and they really understand and understand it (comprehension and understanding). Knowledge, deepening and understanding of this policy will give rise to attitudes of acceptance, neutrality and rejection towards the policy. This attitude will give rise to a disposition in policy actors.

Bureaucratic Structure

Even though the resources to implement a policy are sufficient and the implementers know what and how to do it, and they have the desire to do it. According to Edward III in Widodo (2010: 106), policy implementation may still not be effective due to inefficient bureaucratic structures (deficiencies in bureaucratic structure). This bureaucratic structure includes aspects such as organizational structure, division of authority, relationships between organizational units within the organization concerned, and organizational relationships with outside organizations and so on. Therefore, the bureaucratic structure includes dimensions of fragmentation and standard operating procedures that will facilitate and standardize actions and policy implementers in carrying out their duties. The fragmentation dimension emphasizes that a fragmented bureaucratic structure can increase communication failures, where policy implementers will have a greater chance that their instructions will be distorted.

According to researchers, participation between organizational units can be seen as a part of gluing, aligning, or integrating the work implementation of each work unit so that it becomes a unified work mechanism that is cohesive and directed towards a previously determined goal and target. Apart from that, through working relationships between units, various problems and obstacles to waste management policies can be minimized. According to researchers, the lack of cross-sector and cross-agency cooperation means that this policy is not working well, all forms of punishment and sanctions contained in Morowali Regency Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2017 cannot be realized. Apart from the lack of public awareness of the importance of disposing of waste in its proper place, the location of the TPA (Final Disposal Site) is far away, and only a few trucks carrying waste are a few problems for which the stakeholders have not yet found a solution. For example, in Labota Village, there is only one garbage truck, while the amount of waste production in Bahodopi District reaches 80 tons per day. Even then, the garbage truck is only able to transport 2 trucks a day, so this condition inevitably causes the garbage to pile up. The Head of the Morowali Environmental Service previously said that the waste transport vehicles in the form of 2 dump trucks were ready to be unloaded. However, for handling that requires quick action, Mr Kadis said that everything was handed over to the Bumdes of each village. Thus, the prospects for effective policy implementation are largely determined by accurate and consistent inter-organizational relationships. Apart from that, communication and coordination are mechanisms that have quite an important position in the implementation of waste management policies.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research conducted in Bahodopi District, it can be concluded that the implementation of waste management policies is relatively ineffective. Several aspects cause this policy to be relatively unsuccessful, namely that there are still many violations committed by members of the public. Apart from that, communication between organizations has not been effective, communication between the Environmental Service, District Government and Village Government has not been optimal, and outreach to the community seems half-hearted. The

existing resources in Bahodopi District are still very minimal, including the resources of the apparatus that carries out supervision, budget resources and equipment resources in the form of fleet units and waste bins that are needed, all of which is still very worrying because of the region's inability to realize whatever is needed in implementation. waste management policy. Regarding disposition, there is no consistency from the government in providing sanctions to residents who throw rubbish anywhere. Likewise, the bureaucratic structure is related to the absence of operational standards in handling waste management, which results in many violations being committed by community members. Therefore, the active role of all parties is needed so that waste management in Bahodopi District can be resolved, but what is hoped for is not yet fully effective.

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